

PREP-IBISBA

Industrial Biotechnology Innovation and Synthetic Biology Accelerator
Preparatory Phase

Deliverable number: D8.2

**Preliminary architecture for the IBISBA digital
infrastructure**

Planned delivery date (as in DoA): June 2021, M18

Actual submission date: 2nd September 2021, M21

Workpackage: WP8

Workpackage leader: Carole Goble (UNIMAN)

Deliverable leader: Carole Goble (UNIMAN)

Version: 1.0

Dissemination Level	
PU Public	X
CI Classified, as referred to Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

This deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871118.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Summary	3
2	Introduction	3
2.1	EU-IBISBA Digital Infrastructure context	4
3	Results	8
3.1	IBISBA current digital infrastructure support	8
3.1.1	IBISBAHub	9
3.1.2	Other “Knowledge Commons” Tools	11
3.1.3	Facility support for data management and computational processing	12
3.2	Draft architecture for the IBISBA digital infrastructure	14
3.2.1	IBISBA Core Services	15
3.2.2	IBISBA Core services for data preservation and shared storage	19
3.2.3	Computational processing and tools	20
3.2.4	External thematic registries and repositories	21
3.2.5	Capacity Know-how Services	23
3.3	FAIR IBISBA digital Infrastructure and Interoperability Framework	24
	Generic metadata standards and metadata interoperability	26
	Domain and type specific standards for Modular Service interoperability	27
	FAIR Digital Objects	29
	APIs	30
	Persistent Identifiers	30
3.4	Metadata and FAIR Data Services	31
3.5	Intellectual property (IPR), accessibility, availability and licensing	31
3.6	Digital Security	32
3.7	RDM Lifecycle using the proposed digital framework	34
4	Conclusion	35
5	Partners involved in the work	36
6.	Abbreviations	36

1 Summary

IBISBA's mission as a distributed European research infrastructure is to provide world-class cutting-edge research and innovation services enabling the development of biotechnology as a technology cornerstone of the circular bioeconomy. To achieve this, IBISBA integrates Europe's leading public-operated research infrastructure facilities into a coordinated business environment.

The H2020 PRPEP-IBISBA project is designed to finalize the design and prepare IBISBA for future operation. To achieve this the project is organized into several work packages that focus on different aspects of the infrastructure, including its business model, legal structure, and scientific and technological strategy.

Specifically, regarding this report the PREP-IBISBA project sets out to carefully design IBISBA's digital service framework, describing the e-tools and e-infrastructure needed to deliver all IBISBA services and ensure efficient business operations. In this report, we present the first draft of the digital service framework that will be a "blueprint" for further design of the necessary e-tools and e-infrastructure to support EU-IBISBA's science and business processes, and for the FAIR stewardship of its assets (data, models, analytical workflows, SOPs, science processes and so on). The necessary e-infrastructure proposed will be an ecosystem of software utilities and application codes, computational resources, datasets, and data management and analytics platforms. IBISBA's goal is to support FAIR by Design: from the first steps of producing FAIR data and Data Management Planning to the final steps of depositing data in public archives and enabling its reuse. Thus data will need to be managed at every step of the Research Data lifecycle.

The report presents a draft architecture for the IBISBA digital infrastructure, including a FAIR IBISBA digital Infrastructure and Interoperability Framework, and discussions on Intellectual property, Digital security and mapping of services to the RDM Lifecycle. The report concludes with next steps.

2 Introduction

IBISBA's mission as a distributed European research infrastructure is to provide world-class cutting-edge research and innovation services enabling the development of biotechnology as a technology cornerstone of the circular bioeconomy. To achieve this, IBISBA integrates Europe's leading public-operated research infrastructure facilities into a coordinated business environment.

The H2020 PRPEP-IBISBA project is a coordination and support action designed to finalize the design and preparation of IBISBA for future operation. To achieve this the project is organized into several work packages that focus on different aspects of the infrastructure, including its business model, legal structure, scientific and technological strategy, and e-tools and e-infrastructure needs.

This report presents the first draft of a digital service framework that will be a "blueprint" for the necessary e-tools and e-infrastructure to support EU-IBISBA's science and business processes and for the FAIR stewardship of its assets (data, models, analytical workflows, SOPs, science processes and so on). Standardized metadata and methods are essential for good asset stewardship, the exchange of data, and the representation of common processes: to bridge the development stages (biocatalyst design, experiments, process and product development) and to enable the translation of knowledge into innovative designs (catalysts, engineering processes).

FAIR principles encourage good data management practices and are gaining significant international traction as well as among the European funding bodies such as EOSC and Horizon Europe. Due to the interdisciplinary nature of the field, data arising from Industrial Biotechnology research is a complex mix of computational studies, such as modelling and simulation, and the results of wet-lab experiments construction and experimental characterization. At each stage of the DBTL cycle the size and complexity of data generated keeps increasing, mandating relevant tools and guidance to organize, store, reuse and preserve data. It is therefore important for IBISBA to follow FAIR principles to better manage the data and hence make research more productive for researchers and their collaborators.

One of IBISBA's goals is to support FAIR by Design: from the first steps of producing FAIR data and Data Management Planning to the final steps of depositing data in public archives and enabling its reuse. Thus, data will need to be managed at every step of the Research Data lifecycle as defined by ELIXIR's RDM toolkit RDMKit¹ - Plan, Collect, Process, Analyse, Preserve, Share, Reuse. The RDMkit and its associated tools (Data Stewardship Wizard) and registries (TeSS, FAIRsharing, bio.tools, WorkflowHub) will be incorporated into IBISBA's digital framework.

The necessary e-infrastructure proposed will be an ecosystem of software utilities and application codes, computational resources, datasets, and data management and analytics platforms. E-Infrastructure services will draw upon and operate at the European level with fellow ESFRIs (notably ELIXIR and the EOSC-Life cluster) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), operating with local and national services within EU-IBISBA nodes and national facilities. Plans to train technical and research staff in stewardship and the use of the e-Infrastructure will be presented in Deliverable 8.4.

A "sandbox" implementation of the digital infrastructure will act as a reference implementation, enabling us to review the readiness level of the services offered by prior work performed in the framework of initiatives, such as the H2020 project entitled IBISBA1.0, other European projects and by the wider academic community, and commercial enterprises. The sandbox will be reported in Deliverable 8.4.

2.1 EU-IBISBA Digital Infrastructure context

EU-IBISBA is conceived as a distributed research infrastructure². A distributed partnership of autonomous facilities, each varying in their unique competencies and capabilities to contribute to the DBTL-S lifecycle of Industrial Biotechnology projects, is planned to be organized into a network of national nodes. will be a centralized hub for operating and coordinating the infrastructure and the projects it undertakes; running a common service access point and sharing business practices; and strategic planning, communications and the international collaborations required of an ESFRI. The power of EU-IBISBA is the coordination and monitoring of modular services offered by leading research facilities across Europe (Figure 1).

Mirroring this, the supporting digital infrastructure will need to be similarly federated, to serve the operation of the infrastructure and support the delivery of IBISBA's multi-facility service offerings,

¹ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>

² 2021 IBISBA Report Current Status, [10.34701/ibisba.1.document.34.1](https://doi.org/10.34701/ibisba.1.document.34.1)

following the FAIR principles³ of data and other FAIR Digital Object⁴ management. Whilst computational modular services (computational workflows, model prediction) are intrinsic to model-based synthetic biology, experiences from IBISBA1.0 suggest that the majority of the activities in IBISBA will be wet-lab based. In most of the projects, data will be generated and analysed. Data collection, storage, transfer, processing, and analysis (through automated pipelines for example) and sharing, will need to be delivered and supported through a combination of local and centralised services and resources. These will be operated as a mixture of on-premise and cloud-based digital infrastructure developed and hosted by IBISBA and resources provided by the EOSC, other RI such as ELIXIR, RI Clusters such as EOSC-Life, and community public resources. Deliverable 8.1 presents a review of the EU e-Infrastructure landscape.

Figure 1: IBISBA's putative organisation, from 2021 IBISBA Report Current Status.

Modular services and meta-protocols

An internal IBISBA task force (the so-called SMaRT task force) delivered a service modularisation guideline and a project reporting template to be implemented, for the TNAs in the short term, with a possibility of it being adopted as guidelines for all future EU-IBISBA projects.

Service modularisation enables the participating institutions to modularize their services and provide adequate and sufficient information to plan, negotiate, and execute projects efficiently. It mainly focused on identifying the core functionality, selecting the boundaries (start and end points of a module), identifying and specifying the inputs and outputs, and finally defining the metadata. In the case of the TNAs each facility must have at least one service module for each project they are part of and the multi-facility projects are split into one service module per participating facility.

From experience in the IBISBA1.0 TNAs **modular services** offered by the facilities are chiefly in two forms:

- enzyme screening, cultivation, bioprocess optimization, scale-up of various organisms etc described using lab protocols unique to each facility but reported in a standardised format;

³ FAIR data

⁴ FDO

- computational related services such as omics analysis and pathway design using models and computational workflows.

PREP-IBISBA WP3 proposes that there will be two types of services in future IBISBA; Standardized Integrated Services and Collaborative R&D Services. Regardless of the nature of services, all work will be conducted according to the future quality standards of IBISBA resulting in datasets and outputs. The standards outlined in the Service Modularisation document can hence be extended to the future IBISBA services.

IBISBA provides its experimental services in the form of meta-protocols - modular project workflows that link the services together to execute a project (Figure 2). These require dynamic and flexible support by the digital infrastructure. Data format standards have to be adhered to for harmonising service hand-offs, and all digital objects will need to be secure and held in trusted repositories for long term access.

Figure 2: Modular workflows coordinating modular services, described using TasCu, inputs and outputs defined using standards and contents managed by IBISBAHub, from 2021 IBISBA Report Current Status

The **digital object assets** expected to be managed by IBISBA, along with their metadata, include:

- Information on facilities, people and skills shared;
- Modular services offered and operated by facilities, defined and shared;
- Data
 - data files of different types stored and indexed;
 - data held in different specialised repositories
 - data templates and formats defined and shared;
- Manual Processes
 - facility lab protocols and standard operating procedures definition and exchange;
 - pan-facility project meta-protocols (workflows / scientific processes) linking the modular services operated by the facilities, definition, reporting and execution;

- Computational processes
 - computational models (SBML, SBOL, MATLAB etc) storage and simulation;
 - analytical, computational workflows and data pipelines (Galaxy, KNIME, snakemake etc) creation, execution and exchange;
 - electronic lab notebooks;
- Other files
 - documents, publications and presentations storage and indexed;

All assets should carry metadata markup that is compatible and compliant with EOSC and ESFRI standards, and be exchanged using portable formats developed by the wider LS RI community. All assets should be indexable and accessible by search engines given appropriate accessibility permissions defined by IBISBA data governance and project clients.

The **stakeholders and users** of the digital infrastructure include:

- **IBISBA Clients** seeking offers of the modular services
- **IBISBA Central & Nodes** seeking oversight and monitoring of projects, services and operations, as well as analytics
- **Facility Operators** who will co-develop the scientific processes with the clients to deliver the projects
- **IBISBA Stewards** for data, processes and standards, and maintaining the currency of the modular services
- **IBISBA Trainers** tasked with training Facility Operators with the operating norms of IBISBA and the expectations of RDM for IBISBA modular services
- **IBISBA DevOps** developing and operating the infrastructure

The digital infrastructure will need to:

1. **manage projects from proposal submission and planning through to execution and reporting and dissemination (IBISBA Clients, IBISBA Central, Facility Operators, IBISBA Stewards)**
 - coordinate and monitor the running of modular services through explicitly defined meta-protocols (business and scientific processes) - the business process layer in Figure 3;
 - manage reporting of projects
 - manage a trusted "Knowledge Commons" single entry point to the digital assets of IBISBA, including IBISBAHub;
 - manage a "one shop shop" single entry point to the modular services operated by the facilities of IBISBA;
 - respect IPR and access to project outcomes.
2. **source and manage shared computational, storage and hosting services (IBISBA DevOps, Facility Operators)**
 - for the knowledge commons, one stop shop, and meta-protocols;
 - integrate the above with the autonomous and independently managed data management resources of the facilities and the national nodes, each varying in their digital competencies;

- integrate the above with the computational modular services provided by facilities, and where necessary identify centralised support.
- 3. define and manage the harmonisation and operation of the digital infrastructure (Facility Operators, IBISBA Stewards, IBISBA Trainers)**
- standards and practices for FAIR data, model and lab protocol management, and establish criteria for reviewing and onboarding tools;
 - governance, oversight and long-term preservation of, and access to, IBISBA’s digital assets;
 - a handbook and guidelines for operating the digital infrastructure;
 - training to use the infrastructure.
- 4. support the activities of IBISBA infrastructure and IBISBACentral, through the trusted Knowledge Commons (IBISBACentral & Nodes)**
- retain the results of IBISBA’s activities and projects and manage reporting of results to clients;
 - monitor and report the impact of RI;
 - advertise modular services, people and expertise;
 - share knowledge across IBISBA for standardised protocols, FAIR data management and data quality control;
 - present a public facing interface for searching and accessing IBISBA assets, given appropriate accessibility permissions defined by IBISBA data governance and project clients.

Figure 3: A knowledge commons for coordinating processes and services across facilities, from 2021 IBISBA Report Current Status

3 Results

3.1 IBISBA current digital infrastructure support

IBISBA1.0 implemented a pilot digital infrastructure which EU-IBISBA will build upon. IBISBA1.0 undertook the following:

- deployed and developed a centralised, customised platform to manage the IBISBA Knowledge Commons (IBISBAHub) with associated tools, reported in "IBISBA1.0 Deliverable D7.3 IBISBAHub Workflow Repository and Portal" and described in the IBISBA Handbook⁵;
- sourced RI and community services and platforms for IBISBA assets and data management;
- outsourced and deployed a web portal for a one stop shop (OSS) of modular services;
- explored mechanisms for defining and managing the scientific processes (meta-protocols) that coordinate modular services across facilities, reported in "IBISBA1.0 Deliverable D7.4 BPM Demonstrator";
- built a library of computational workflows (registered in EOSC-Life's WorkflowHub) and lab protocols (registered in IBISBAHub and protocols.io), reported in "IBISBA1.0 Deliverable D7.1 A library of workflows and workflow nodes";
- set standards for FAIR protocols and workflows ("IBISBA Deliverable D7.2 Workflow metadata specification for Industrial Biotech workflows and nodes") and data formats, terms, and identifiers.

3.1.1 IBISBAHub

Central to the IBISBA Knowledge Commons is the IBISBAHub. This is a shared space for recording, accessing and sharing the digital object assets of IBISBA and its projects. IBISBA members can manage projects, register a large variety of data objects (e.g. experimental outputs, sample information, documents, presentations) with associated metadata and in addition manage the accessibility of the content. Thus the Hub provides an online portal and catalogue for IBISBA Assets and project results with access to a range of services:

- A "yellow pages" of people, organisation, facilities and their expertise. This could be extended to include modular services;
- Self-manage project assets, organising, sharing, and disseminating assets arising from multipartner collaborations, as well as project events.
 - The Hub catalogues project outcomes, SOPs, workflows, template library, and small file repository, and indexes large data files held either in-house or in external repositories and registries;
 - The Hub catalogues or stores project data outcomes for service handoffs between the modular services operated by facilities;
 - The Hub enables fine grained access permissions for all objects directly under the control of the project managers. Access can be provided to the external customer(s) and possibly reviewer(s);
 - Projects assets are organised against the structure of the DBTL-S scientific workflow (meta-protocol) developed for each project.
- Manage data resources, using IBISBAHub either as a primary user management resource, or as a complement to local resources. There is currently a limit as to the size of asset that can be uploaded to IBISBAHub. The mapping of assets to a GitHub repository is already being developed. The Hub ensures that the data is stored securely, privately and can still be shared or published when ready.

⁵ <https://ibisba.github.io/handbook/index.html>

- Store, register, share and/or access standardised protocols, shared computational workflows and data format templates;
- Describe and inter-relate data assets using rich metadata relevant for samples, organisms, models, protocols, data, computational workflows and documents;
- Integrate with third-party tools, such as modelling tools (e.g. JWS Online), metadata capture tools (e.g. Rightfield) and development repositories (e.g. GitHub). The Hub supports an OpenAPI⁶ and JSONAPI⁷ conformant interface that supports secured programmatic access for tools.
- Report on projects, using the IBISBAHub contents as raw material to compile reports, for clients, the infrastructure and the EC.

Figure 4: IBISBAHub Project structure for a TNA Project, organised to reflect the DBTL-S stages of the scientific process

The IBISBAHub currently has registered: 46 projects, 135 people; 42 investigations, 65 data files; 8 workflows. IBISBAHub is built on the FAIRDOME-SEEK platform, also used by ELIXIR Nodes and is production-level TRL8.

A comprehensive *Handbook*⁸ provides a guide to use the Hub, practical instructions on how to write and curate protocols and information on IBISBA to both its members and IBISBA's user community. The handbook is a living document and is being expanded continuously beyond IBISBA 1.0 to become an operational handbook for EU-IBISBA.

⁶ <https://swagger.io/specification/>

⁷ <https://jsonapi.org/>

⁸ <https://ibisba.github.io/handbook/index.html>

3.1.2 Other “Knowledge Commons” Tools

Alongside IBISBAHub are a number of tools developed internally by IBISBA or provided by external service providers (Table 1) that IBISBA partners and clients may already use. These organise and manage Hub content, or provide additional registries or services that support the RDM lifecycle. All stages related to RDM should be built around IBISBAHub.

Service	Description	Provider
The One Stop Shop & Service Catalogue	Website built on a CMS to list the service offerings. Built on eZ Platform 2.5 but outsourced and without means to update.	Internal PRUAB
Galaxy-SynBioCAD ⁹	Galaxy instance for model SynBio workflows. Independent Galaxy instance operated by INRAE as a modular service; workflows registered in IBISBAHub and WorkflowHub	Internal INRAE
JWS Online ¹⁰ COPASI ¹¹	SBML model simulation services JWS Online Managed by U Stellenbosch, service hosted by the FAIRDOM Consortium. JWS Online is also a model repository The COPASI project is an international collaboration between three groups at the Biocomplexity Institute of Virginia Tech , the University of Heidelberg , and the University of Connecticut, UConn Health .	External FAIRDOM COPASI
TasCu ¹²	a metaprotocol editing tool, helper tool for IBISBAHub to structure the content to match the modular services and their inputs and outputs. Produces a CSV file to seed IBISBAHub entry for a project. Small web application, not in active development	Internal VTT
iPOP	a metaprotocol spreadsheet tool for populating IBISBAHub. Integrated into IBISBAHub	Internal UNIMAN

⁹ <https://galaxyproject.org/use/synbiocad/>

¹⁰ <https://jjj.biochem.sun.ac.za/>

¹¹ <http://copasi.org/>

¹² <https://tascu.vtt.fi>

Rightfield ¹³	a metadata template spreadsheet tool Small desktop application developed by the FAIRDOM Consortium	External FAIRDOM
ELIXIR-AAI ¹⁴ / LS-AAI	Authentication and Authorisation system Operated by ELIXIR	External ELIXIR
WorkflowHub ¹⁵	Rich registry for computational workflows Used to register IBISBA computational workflows, catalogued in turn in IBISBAHub. operated by ELIXIR and the EOSC-Life Cluster	External ELIXIR
Bio.tools ¹⁶	registry of computational tools Used to register IBISBA computational tools. operated by ELIXIR	External ELIXIR
Protocols.io ¹⁷	Registry for SOPs and lab protocols Freemium	External, Commercial
IBISBA Handbook ¹⁸	The IBISBA handbook for projects and using the IBISBAHub and its helper software Based on Github, an external service	Internal UNIMAN WUR

Table 1 IBISBA current registries and tools to manage digital assets across the RDM life cycle

3.1.3 Facility support for data management and computational processing

In IBISBA the work of the modular services is carried out at partner facilities. Assets for IBISBA may be uploaded to IBISBAHub or maybe stored by a member facility and registered in IBISBAHub.

Current facility-level data support practices were identified through experiences of operating TNA projects in IBISBA1.0 and a survey of the facility operators. As yet no National Nodes forming networks of facilities with dedicated node digital infrastructure have been established.

TransNational Access (TNA) provided subsidised access to specialised research facilities in IBISBA1.0. So far 5 TNA applications have been launched. The TNA projects could either be carried out in a single facility or executed as multi facility projects. Data generated from various TNA projects was typically

¹³ <https://rightfield.org.uk/>

¹⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/services/compute/aa1>

¹⁵ <https://workflowhub.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://bio.tools/>

¹⁷ <https://www.protocols.io/>

¹⁸ <https://ibisba.github.io/handbook/>

stored locally in the facility and handed-over to the next facility mostly via emails, in the case of multi-facility projects. For the first three TNA's the projects were encouraged but not mandated to use the IBISBAHub for data registration and preservation. As a consequence the TNA's possibly have PDF's or .docx files as digital objects which are not centrally stored and may or may not conform to IBISBA data and metadata standards and formats.

From TNA₄ onwards registering all projects and the related input/output data on IBISBAHub was made compulsory. The access and sharing rights are strictly decided by the data owner.

A *survey* gathered information about the existing e-infrastructure and data management practices in the facilities currently supporting EU-IBISBA. The survey was designed for IBISBA facility operators and team members carrying out the IBISBA projects to assess the support available to conduct EU-IBISBA's science and business processes and FAIR stewardship of its assets. The [survey](#)¹⁹ of 16 questions had a subset focusing on the type of hardware such as compute, storage and cloud services available for everyday usage as well as long-term storage and preservation. The remaining questions explored the software aspects of data security, transfer, access rights, digital cataloguing and metadata collection. The survey also asked about the awareness of FAIR principles and their level of application, if any, practiced by the facilities.

The survey received 9 responses (out of 21 entities targeted). Its results reveal that data management practices are currently below the standards level required for future operation of IBISBA. Most facilities are lacking central storage, where data can be collected or maintained in a systematic and secure fashion. Moreover, most data sharing uses email or transfer across a local network. The survey revealed that data management policy was often absent or insufficiently explicit and no metadata collection software is as yet deployed. Among facility operator respondents, the FAIR principles are insufficiently assimilated and when they are, they are not yet properly implemented, often due to a lack of know-how and/or training.

It is essential for facilities to:

- upload project data to IBISBAHub for safe and secure data management, sharing and storage;
- or
- register project data in IBISBAHub and *guarantee* permanent accessibility to that data.

Those facilities that insist on registration and retention must be verified to have data management policies and regulations in place, and Trusted Repositories certified by, for example, Core Trust Seal.

Data will need to be transferred between facilities or national node stores. Cloud Storage Services for Synchronization and Sharing (CS₃)²⁰ are typically deployed by e-infrastructure providers, NRENs (National Research & Education Networks) and major research institutions, and are in the daily workflows for users, including researchers, students, scientists and engineers. CS₃ Services include: Dropbox, Sharepoint, Nextcloud, Owncloud, Powerfolder, Pydio, Seafiler, and Syncany. Other transfer services such as Globus support large scale transfer.

¹⁹ https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1UWKvn67tv8yNQ8HgSTCtMuljarBoVj6L1qvOC_k78-s/edit

²⁰ <https://www.cs3community.org/>

3.2 Draft architecture for the IBISBA digital infrastructure

Figure 5 sets out the draft architecture for the IBISBA digital infrastructure.

Figure 5: Draft architecture for the IBISBA digital infrastructure. *Italics indicate resources that may be used.* The green shaded components are the IBISBA Core and specific to the RI. Other components may be sourced from external service providers and tailored with IBISBA-specific content or IBISBA-specific installations. External services may be drawn from ESFRIs, EOSC, commercial and community sources (see Deliverable 8.1)

As foreshadowed, the approach is a federation of services and resources, including the exploitation of external repositories and registries and local facility/node based storage and compute provision. The options around centrally provided and locally provided storage and compute for facilities is discussed in section 3.2.2. The AAI, metadata and API framework that supports the integration of the services is discussed in section 3.3.

In EU-IBISBA, mission critical resources will be controlled directly by IBISBA through its Nodes or IBISBACentral. Wherever possible the number of platforms should be small and streamlined.

The green shaded components of Figure 5 are the **IBISBA Core** and IBISBA specific. Other components may be sourced from external service providers and tailored with IBISBA-specific content or IBISBA-specific installations. External services may be drawn from ESFRIs, EOSC, commercial and community sources (see Del 8.1).

External repositories and registries will be selected for their unique features and content but also for their role in the ecosystem, openness and sustainability. The aim is to create dedicated IBISBA collections in these resources and link to them from the IBISBAHub and Website.

It is the combination of registry collections and IBISBA Core (IBISBAHub, Dashboard, One Stop Shop, Website) that make up the Knowledge Commons.

3.2.1 IBISBA Core Services

The infrastructure is built around **IBISBAHub**, a powerful central registry (“Hub”). The Hub organises in one place two major classes of IBISBA assets:

- **the outcomes of projects** based on their steps and the modular services those steps have executed. The Hub is cornerstone for any project, and is the handing off point for the inputs and outputs of services, a repository for long term preservation of results and derived datasets and a knowledge source for reporting to clients, facilities and IBISBACentral and nodes. All project related data and metadata should be exchanged between partners and facilities within the same project.
- **knowledge about IBISBA**, its people and facilities, standards, data templates and lab protocols; models and workflows developed by the partners, training material etc.

The Hub registers or stores and links together entries in the local data stores of facilities and external thematic registries/repositories, creating an integrated view of knowledge, and projects and their results regardless of the type of object (SOP, model, workflow, data etc) or its physical location. The Hub is not currently expected to be the long term repository for large primary datasets, but instead reference their repositories. In this way the Hub can be viewed as a federated catalogue, analogous to the efforts of other ESRIs: the SHHOC Service Catalogue, or the planned federated catalogues of ENVRI-FAIR and PaNOSC²¹, and the Research Product Catalogues of the Minimal Viable EOSC by the Architecture WG and reported in the EOSC Interoperability Framework. For some of its asset types the Hub uses the same registries as EOSC-Life and ELIXIR.

The Hub’s cataloging features are tailored to support IBISBA projects in specific ways, notably:

- *project-centric* cataloguing of datasets and outcomes with detailed permissions limiting access;
- *in-flight* organisation of datasets and outcomes as the projects are being executed, supporting and reflecting the tailored DBTL-S meta-protocols for each project;
- *interlinked* organization of different kinds of outcomes - models, data, workflows etc - and datatypes arising from the inherently interdisciplinary nature of the DBTL-S process of Industrial Biotechnology.

IBISBAHub will be directly managed by EU-IBISBA and operated under the data governance of IBISBACentral and its policies. IBISBAHub will be expected to adhere to EOSC certification for FAIR compliance for its content and for the registry itself, and obtain appropriate certification²² and as Trusted Repository, for example from Core Trust Seal²³.

²¹ Carole Goble, & Nick Juty. (2021). Analysis of existing research data cataloguing efforts towards integrated discovery. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4693217>

²² L'Hours, Hervé, & Huigen, Frans. (2020). CoreTrustSeal+FAIR Landscape of Capability Maturity Modeling - A FAIRsFAIR Discussion Paper (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4005598>

²³ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

Figure 6: IBISBAHub Yellow Pages of Institution - which could be extended to be facilities and services

The **One Stop Shop (OSS)** is a client facing web portal that lists the modular service offerings of the IBISBA facilities. As figure 6 shows, the IBISBAHub's yellow pages contain information on members and their organisations. This facility information is easy to directly manage and update, and can be expanded to include information on service offerings. Currently this capability is underused. The current One Stop Shop was outsourced onto a deprecated platform with no means to update, and not integrated into the rest of the infrastructure.

In EU-IBISBA, IBISBAHub could be extended to carry the service catalogue information a streamlined integration of the IBISBA Core services pursued.

The github option is in line with modern web-based development including the IBISBA Handbook and the ELIXIR RDMkit. By adopting a github based approach for the OSS we can harmonise around one web-based platform and institute editorial update processes along the same lines as the Handbook.

The **Dashboard** is a client and IBISBA management facing web portal that presents the status of projects. It will use the IBISBAHub and Project Management subsystem as sources.

The **Project Management sub-system** is specifically tailored to the unique proposition of IBISBA's facility modular services offerings and inter-facility coordination through meta-protocols. This sub-system explicitly supports the scientific and business processes currently being developed in WP6. The operational details are still being developed but we anticipate the following support components:

- **Project proposal review management:** candidate systems include the ESFRI INSTRUCT's *ARIA* cloud services²⁴ used by EOSC-Life to manage open calls, although this is a heavy-weight system and not open source. An alternative is to repurpose a conference reviewing platform such as *EasyChair*²⁵.

²⁴ <https://instruct-eric.eu/help/about-aria>

²⁵ <https://easychair.org/>

- Project planning, initiation and DMP:** the preparation of a meta-protocol plan for coordinating the selected modular services provided by the facilities. The plan is anticipated to be at a coarse granularity, at the level of the service modules, with clean hand-off points based in standardised formats for inputs and outputs and registered protocols operated by the facilities. *TasCu*²⁶ was developed by IBISBA1.0 as a meta-protocol editing tool; an alternative is to use a *spreadsheet template*. The meta-protocol seeds (i) a IBISBAHub entry for a project using the *iPOP tool* (ii) the project management and execution subsystem and (iii) outcome reporting for the Dashboard. The projects need to assemble a Data Management Plan.

Figure 7: IBISBAHub extension to generate a BPM in a standard notation.

- Project management and execution:** The meta-protocol will be converted into an events-based business process, to monitor and guide the progress of a project: when is a step completed, hand-off points, where should data be registered, who is responsible etc. The fine-grained protocols, internal to facilities, are considered to be encapsulated steps to be independently managed by the facility, and are not coordinated at this level. Consequently they must be registered in the Hub for review and quality control. IBISBA1.0 Del 7.4 reported on the possibility of generating a Business Process Model (BPM) for an IBISBA project and loading it into a BPM system that then supports its enactment BPM systems support the concept of participants in a project - corresponding to the IBISBA facilities. The *Flowable*²⁷ BPM system was selected for trial, to communicate with the assignees of the modular services, and update the IBISBAHub²⁸ automatically by the BPM system. IBISBAHub was extended to support the BPM (Figure 7). Results are encouraging. Other project management systems such as *Trello* may also be deployed. The Dashboard should provide an integrated overview of the status of each project, and outcome reports for clients, facilities and IBISBACentral should be generated (at least in part) automatically.
- Project reporting.** The IBISBA SMaRT task force created a unified project reporting template for different recipients (the EC, IBISBA or the clients) with the aim of making it pragmatic and useful for both current and future IBISBA projects. These pilot reporting templates will be improved and adapted in accordance with requirements.

²⁶ <https://tasclu.vtt.fi>

²⁷ Flowable is distributed under the Apache V2 license. The Apache License is a permissive free software license written by the Apache Software Foundation (ASF)

²⁸ This uses IBISBAHub's REST API <https://docs.seek4science.org/help/user-guide/api.html>

The **Facility/Node subsystem links local storage resources to the IBISBAHub**. Based on experiences in IBISBA1.0 the facilities operate largely autonomously. They will have local capabilities to store and archive data for the wet-lab processing undertaken at their site. All are expected to operate their own LIMS systems. Some facilities have the capability to retain long-term, providing authenticated access to primary data generated by their labs. Data integration scenarios include:

- Outcome data is registered and *deposited* into IBISBAHub: this may be manual or automatic, and must be linked to a relevant lab protocol. Data format standards and standards for the inputs/outputs of modular services must be compiled with. Responsibility for data retention and preservation passes to IBISBAHub DevOps.
- Outcome data is registered into IBISBAHub but *retained and stored by the facility*: as above, this may be manual or automatic and protocols and standards must be complied with. However greater responsibility now rests with the facility as the entry in the Hub will be shadowed. In order for data to be FAIR it must be permanently accessible. This requires that each facility:
 - Adhere to IBISBA policy for the creation of standard Global Persistent Identifiers;
 - Implement Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) for access from the IBISBAHub;
 - Have Core Trust Seal²⁹ certification or similar to guarantee long-term preservation
- Outcome data is registered into IBISBAHub and *deposited into a third party thematic repository*: Such a repository will be reviewed and certified by IBISBA policies as appropriate. Experiences from IBISBA1.0 suggest this is a rare scenario. More likely data are deposited into IBISBAHub and then brokered from there into thematic repositories by the project managers. Work in ELIXIR is ongoing to register FAIRDOME-SEEK based Hubs, such as IBISBAHub, into ISA-TAB repositories such as ENA and PRIDE.

IBISBA will be required to access and provide secure data transfer between facilities and the IBISBAHub and between facilities, particularly when automating transfer. Secondary, derived data is small (Gbs) and not a problem to transfer. Image data, for example, is large and incurs transfer costs and dedicated technologies. *Cloud Storage Services for Synchronization and Sharing (CS3)*³⁰ services provide an appropriate mechanism, particularly where facilities do not provide APIs to local data stores. The EU [C₃MESH₄OEOSC](https://www.cs3community.org/)³¹ project to develop standard APIs and become integrated into the EOSC, providing a Pan-European natively FAIR and GDPR compliant data storage and sharing fabric. Each facility will have some kind of institutional CS3 service that is cloud based (OneDrive, Dropbox, OwnCloud, Box etc) or on premise (NextCloud). The best strategy depends on data scales and the capabilities of the facilities. Alternatives for large scale data include *Globus Data Transfer*³² and from the EOSC community includes *EUDAT's B2DROP*³³.

²⁹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.cs3community.org/>

³¹ <https://cs3mesh4eosoc.eu/>

³² <https://www.globus.org/data-transfer>

³³ <https://eudat.eu/services/b2drop>

Data and metadata transferred between Facilities and the Hub will adhere to the IBISBA Interoperability Framework described in Section 3.3.

IBISBA Core Hosting

The hosting for the IBISBA core (IBISBAHub, OSS, website, Dashboard etc.) must be on an infrastructure that is fit for purpose, that is:

- reliable - the services must be available 24/7/365;
- secure - the services must be secured as far as practicable;
- IBISBA controlled - although the services are hosted on the infrastructure it must allow configuration and control by designated IBISBA personnel e.g. IBISBA personnel must be able to reboot when necessary;
- configurable - the infrastructure must allow easy configuration, for example to change the memory allocation of a VM. Changes to the configuration should not affect the visibility nor availability of the IBISBA service;
- upgradable / up-to-date - the infrastructure must support up-to-date operating systems and databases, and the systems should be upgradable by IBISBA personnel;
- allow configuration / control of exposed ports - the infrastructure should not limit the ports that are made available to the services and the ports must be controllable by IBISBA personnel.

Domain name ownership and control must be by IBISBA personnel. Infrastructure is needed for backups including automatic hot switching between Virtual Machines, and to enable Persistent IDs, for example to files, even when they are physically moved. The infrastructure should provide dashboards of useful information and provide timely notification to designated IBISBA personnel of any changes to the services / infrastructure.

IBISBA Core Unified Interaction for Users and AAI

IBISBA Core needs a unified feel for the users, with a single login and single consistent search capability. All IBISBA assets, services and concepts must have an easily identifiable and single URL; for example, the service offered by a facility must have the same identifier in the website, one stop shop, Hub etc.

A single Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) system should be common across all of the IBISBA Core and its registries. IBISBAHub already implements ELIXIR AAI/LS-Login - many of the other registries proposed to be used by IBISBA (section 3.2.4) implement the same AAI system.

3.2.2 IBISBA Core services for data preservation and shared storage

IBISBA will need to have long-term access to primary data that will be expected to be retained and preserved for the benefit of IBISBA, its partners and its clients. This primary data will be catalogued in the IBISBAHub; some will be stored by a facility using their own resources and will have to sign a SLA to EU-IBISBA to guarantee preservation and access.

IBISBA Core needs access to fast and extensible storage, supporting large files (as identified by IBISBA). Files may be moved from short term to longer term and then archive storage. File movement should be hidden from the users (as far as practicable) and the storage must appear as if it is on the service, i.e. not NFS.

We will need to provision **shared storage** to support an IBISBA filestore for the IBISBA Core and available to the facilities/nodes. Storage may be supplied by an EOSC service provider (e.g. EUDAT³⁴), national cloud provider (e.g. SURF-SARA iRODS³⁵), commercial cloud provider (AWS S3³⁶) or an IBISBA node (e.g. WUR's iRODS platform). We may operate our own data storage as on-premise or cloud. We will need to support a three-tiered data storage (hot, warm, archived) model depending on data sizes, and have preservation services in place to be Core Trust Seal certified.

3.2.3 Computational processing and tools

HPC and HTC computational processing for model simulation and computational workflows (dry-lab) is expected to be relatively episodic (infrequent) and comparatively modest in computational capacity requirements. We make this assumption based on the TNAs and projects in IBISBA1.0, where wet-lab activities dominate and computational services are confined to specific modular services offered by a facility - these facilities typically have local capabilities and capacities for computational processing or their own cloud computing arrangements.

IBISBA will need to investigate the provisioning of or access to a shared compute and VM hosting service, using cloud or a mix of on-premise and cloud. This would be made available to those partners offering computational services. A number of candidate suppliers are registered in the EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace³⁷ and highlighted in Deliverable D8.1, including the EGI Federation³⁸ and commercial providers brokered by OCRE³⁹.

All tools will be encouraged to be containerised and images placed stored in container stores or registries (e.g. DockerHub⁴⁰, Quay.io⁴¹) sponsored by IBISBA where fees are due.

All tools will be registered in IBISBAHub and where possible with the ELIXIR bio.tools registry⁴² in an IBISBA Collection, and containers registered with ELIXIR biocontainers registry⁴³.

The prime computational services offered by IBISBA1.0 are the following:

Tools

Tools provided by the IBISBA partners as part of their Service offerings⁴⁴ and general tools such as Electronic Lab Notebooks, for example Jupyter Notebooks⁴⁵.

Model simulation

³⁴ <https://eudat.eu/>

³⁵ <https://userinfo.surfsara.nl/systems/data-archive>

³⁶ <https://aws.amazon.com>

³⁷ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

³⁸ <https://www.egi.eu/federation/>

³⁹ <https://www.ocre-project.eu/services/cloud-suppliers#>

⁴⁰ <https://hub.docker.com/>

⁴¹ <https://quay.io/>

⁴² <https://bio.tools/>

⁴³ <https://biocontainers.pro/>

⁴⁴ <https://hub.ibisba.eu/nodes>

⁴⁵ <https://jupyter.org/>

Systems such as JWS Online and COPASI simulate SBML models and are integrated into FAIRDOMHub, a sister of IBISBAHub. JWS Online is already integrated with IBISBAHub.

Computational workflows

A Galaxy instance (*Galaxy-SynBioCAD*⁴⁶) is operated as a partner operated service for IBISBA. IBISBA1.0 developed a library of workflows that incorporate containerised modelling and prediction tools⁴⁷, some implemented in the KNIME workflow system. Galaxy was adopted to provide a one-stop shop for computational workflows that is easier to use. The current host is a Linux virtual machine with 64GB, 8 CPUs 2GHz and 200GB of disk. This seems underpowered and there are issues of co-location of data to processing. An alternative is to partner with ELIXIR and Galaxy Europe and deploy Galaxy-SynBioCAD on Galaxy-Europe, making use of their Pulsar compute platform.

EOSC-Life has developed a Workflow Collaboratory⁴⁸ comprising a full set of services and resources for end to end workflow lifecycle management and execution which is workflow management system agnostic. This includes: support for *Galaxy-Europe*⁴⁹ as well as other workflow systems such as *Snakemake* and *Nextflow*; services for workflow monitoring, benchmarking and execution; and WorkflowHub⁵⁰, a Workflow Registry based on the FAIRDOM-SEEK platform which also underpins IBISBAHub. The Collaboratory implements GA4GH APIs for seamless integration and a metadata framework for interoperability; IBISBA currently exposes its registered workflows as GA4GH tools⁵¹. WorkflowHub has a community dedicated to supporting the registration and management of workflows.

The WorkflowHub will be the canonical registry of workflows for IBISBA in a dedicated IBISBA Team [WorkflowHub in a curated collection](#)⁵², and referenced by IBISBAHub through proxies. A direct link to Galaxy-SynBioCAD established with WorkflowHub will support direct launching and results will be registered and stored in IBISBAHub. The proposed IBISBA interoperability Framework (section 3) is compliant with the EOSC-Life workflow collaboratory metadata framework and the ELIXIR Tools ecosystem.

3.2.4 External thematic registries and repositories

Wherever possible we will use infrastructures developed and supported by other RIs, notably those in the EOSC-Life Cluster / LS-RI⁵³, partnering where appropriate. There are IBISBA assets that are suitable for inclusion in external registries and repositories and would be better held there; the previous section gives examples of bio.tools and WorkflowHub registries.

To create an integrated, unified view of assets in IBISBAHub, content held in other registries and repositories will be shadowed and proxied by the Hub. IBISBAHub workflows will show workflows

⁴⁶ <https://galaxyproject.org/use/synbiocad/>

⁴⁷ IBISBA1.0 Deliverable D7.1 A library of workflows and workflow nodes

⁴⁸ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/achievements/>

⁴⁹ <https://usegalaxy.eu/>

⁵⁰ <https://workflowhub.org>

⁵¹ <https://workflowhub.eu/ga4gh/trs/v2/tools>

⁵² <https://workflowhub.eu/projects/1>

⁵³ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>

where the main entry is in WorkflowHub, and tools where the main entry is in bio.tools. When proxying, all retrieval of data is forwarded to the proxied asset and no information would be kept on IBISBAHub apart from the PID of the proxied asset (and access information). When shadowing, some metadata about the asset is stored on IBISBAHub, for example the title, license and creators. The storage of this metadata ensures that the current IBISBAHub search mechanisms would not be affected. For other information, such as the asset itself, that is normally done by a call to the shadowed asset (as with proxying).

Shadowing goes hand in hand with synchronisation with the external resource, which must be a FAIR registry/repository with accessible PIDs and a long term preservation policy. Any information in the Hub must be kept consistent with that for the remote asset and mirrored in the IBISBAHub asset. Various synchronization mechanisms have been considered: including Apache Kafka⁵⁴, RabbitMQ⁵⁵, Webhooks⁵⁶ or WebSub⁵⁷.

Data may be archived, deposited in trusted community public archives such as those offered by ELIXIR [Core Data Resources](#)⁵⁸ and [Deposition Databases](#)⁵⁹, (including [MetaboLights](#)⁶⁰, [IntAct](#)⁶¹, [BioSamples](#)⁶², [BioModels](#)⁶³, and [Reactome](#)⁶⁴); repositories specialising in Synthetic Biology such as for parts (SynBioHub⁶⁵, and JBEI ICE⁶⁶), and models (JWS Online, BioModels). ELIXIR has recently started work on “data brokering” pipelines - that is moving data from project resources such as IBISBAHub to ELIXIR public archives. IBISBAHub can reference entries in these Trusted Repositories and may need to implement brokering pipelines. CDRs are part of ELIXIR’s sustainability effort of the [Global Biodata Coalition](#)⁶⁷.

Commercial repositories also offer rich services that would be beneficial to IBISBA and widen its impact and penetration; for example protocols.io offers a “freemium” service for SOPs and lab protocols. *IBISBA has started a workspace in protocols.io*⁶⁸.

Contributing to EOSC Services

⁵⁴ <https://kafka.apache.org/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

⁵⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Webhook>

⁵⁷ <https://w3c.github.io/websub/>

⁵⁸ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/core-data-resources>

⁵⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

⁶⁰ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

⁶¹ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/intact/>

⁶² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/>

⁶³ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/biomodels/>

⁶⁴ <https://reactome.org/>

⁶⁵ <https://synbiohub.org/>

⁶⁶ <https://public-registry.jbei.org/login>

⁶⁷ <https://globalbiodata.org/>

⁶⁸ <https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/ibisba>

IBISBAHub already has the ability for snapshots of assets to have an associated DOI and to be registered in Zenodo⁶⁹ by the user. Zenodo is part of the OpenAIRE⁷⁰ EOSC Infrastructure. OpenAIRE is a world-wide CRIS (Current research information system) serving funders, projects, organizations, and authors, and supports the aggregation of research products (pubs, datasets, software) from community repositories. It provides additional services including a Research Graph, community dashboards and monitoring dashboards.

IBISBAHub should be a feed service for OpenAIRE through its Bioschemas and RO-Crate support. The OpenAIRE Research Graph could be a useful resource to enrich the Hub. IBISBA should review the benefits of an OpenAIRE community dashboard to monitor ESFRI's impact. However, an issue is that OpenAIRE is about open research, and most of the Hub content is not expected to be open.

[EOSC Portal Catalogue and Marketplace](#)⁷¹ is part of the EOSC implementation roadmap as one of the expected “federating core” services, conceived to “provide a European delivery channel connecting the demand-side and the supply-side of the EOSC”. *IBISBAHub should be registered in the marketplace.*

3.2.5 Capacity Know-how Services

IBISBA will augment its Handbook⁷² with additional services from ELIXIR that will significantly: enable the development of data management capability in the IBISBA Facilities and Nodes, its clients and outside in the wider community and raise the profile of IBISBA.

- **FAIRsharing**⁷³ A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies. *IBISBAHub should be registered and make FAIRsharing collections for standards and deposition databases for IBISBA projects.*
- **FAIRAssist** A decision making tool for choosing public deposition databases, to be released in 2021.
- **ELIXIR Data Stewardship Wizard**⁷⁴ A powerful decision support tool for creating Smart Data Management Plans. Data Stewards capture and combine their knowledge and expertise with respect to the specific needs of a domain or an organisation. Researchers are guided through composing a DMP which can be then exported using selected template and format, including machine-actionable; integrated with FAIRsharing and RDMkit. *IBISBAHub should develop customized DMPs for projects using DSW, and build a pool of DMPs.*
- **TeSS**⁷⁵ ELIXIR's Training Portal for browsing, discovering and organising life sciences training resources, aggregated from ELIXIR nodes and 3rd-party providers; integrated with bio.tools and FAIRsharing. *IBISBA should become a source for TeSS and contribute training materials and learning pathways.*

⁶⁹ <https://zenodo.org/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.openaire.eu>

⁷¹ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/>

⁷² <https://ibisba.github.io/handbook/>

⁷³ <https://fairsharing.org>

⁷⁴ <https://ds-wizard.org/>

⁷⁵ <https://tess.elixir-europe.org/>

- **RDMkit**⁷⁶ The ELIXIR Research Data Management toolkit written by life scientists for life scientists to guide FAIR data management throughout the data lifecycle. RDMkit links into content in FAIRsharing, TeSS, bio.tools, (and soon WorkflowHub) and is being integrated with the DSW to create a one-stop shop for knowledge about FAIR Data in the Life Sciences. The contents are generated and maintained by the ELIXIR community and beyond. Pages have already been written on Microbial Biotechnology, and *pages on "Tools Assemblies" should include pages based in IBISBA's infrastructure. IBISBA staff already contribute to RDMkit.*

These resources provide a rich knowledge commons for IBISBA projects and training.

3.3 FAIR IBISBA digital Infrastructure and Interoperability Framework

As part of the EOSC ecosystem, the IBISBA digital infrastructure is expected to adhere to the EOSC FAIR Principles. Not only are the components outlines in section 3.3 expected to be interoperable with each other but also with the wider EOSC ecosystem, aligning with the EOSC Interoperability Framework⁷⁷ and effort towards integrated discovery across ESFRI data catalogues.

The EOSC Interoperability Framework sets out four levels of interoperability: Technical, Semantic, Organisational and Legal (Figure 8). These largely complement the FAIR Data principles, for example on access protocols, metadata, PIDs and licensing. Here we mainly focus on Technical and Semantic levels, and the metadata, formats and APIs need to connect services.

⁷⁶ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

⁷⁷ EOSC interoperability framework Report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Groups FAIR and Architecture <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d787ea54-6a87-11eb-aeb5-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-190308283>

Layer	Recommendation
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Specifications for EOSC Services. • A common security and privacy framework (including Authorisation and Authentication Infrastructure). • Easy-to-understand Service-Level Agreements for all EOSC resource providers. • Easy access to data sources available in different formats. • Coarse-grained and fine-grained dataset (and other research object) search tools. • A clear EOSC PID policy.
Semantic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear and precise, publicly-available definitions for all concepts, metadata and data schemas. • Semantic artefacts preferably with open licenses. • Associated documentation for semantic artefacts. • Repositories of semantic artefacts, rules with a clear governance framework. • A minimum metadata model (and crosswalks) to ease discovery over existing federated research data and metadata. • Extensibility options to allow for disciplinary metadata. • Clear protocols and building blocks for the federation/harvesting of semantic artefacts catalogues.
Organisational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability-focused rules of participation recommendations. • Usage recommendations of standardised data formats and/or vocabularies, and with their corresponding metadata. • A clear management of permanent organisation names and functions.
Legal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised human and machine-readable licenses, with a centralised source of knowledge and support on copyright and licenses. • Permissive licenses for metadata (and preferably for data, whenever possible). And CC0 preferred over CC BY 4.0. • Identification of different parts of a dataset with different licenses. • Clearly marked instances of expired or inexistent copyright, as well as for orphan data. • A clear list of EOSC-recommended licenses and their compatibility with Member States' recommended licenses. • Tracking of license evolution over time for datasets. • Harmonised policy and guidance to dealing with cases where patent filing or trade secrets may be compromised by disclosure. • GDPR-compliance for personal data. • Additional restrictions on access and use of data only applied in cases of applicable legislation or legitimate reasons. • Harmonised terms of use across repositories • Alignment between Member States national legislations and EOSC.

Figure 8 Four layers of interoperability as presented in the EOSC Interoperability Framework. All these criteria must be systematically addressed and supported by the IBISBA digital infrastructure.

Figure 9 IBISBA Interoperability Framework

Generic metadata standards and metadata interoperability

Generic metadata is applicable across multiple data types, and can be broadly considered as resource-specific, rather than data type specific. A number of generic vocabularies exist, largely created to address specific issues, or else to build or repurpose those that existed for a new purpose. Because so many exist it is common practice to develop cross-walks or mappings across the different schema⁷⁸. IBISBAHub and One Stop Shop are key registries that will need to mark up their content in community agreed standards to interoperate with registries such as OpenAIRE, and support federated search and discoverability. They make it possible to have a decentralized approach to publishing data and other object catalogues and makes federated search for datasets across catalogues in multiple sites possible using the same query mechanism and structure. External repositories and registries used by IBISBA will also use these mark-up standards. The terms are normally hidden and invisible to the user.

- Schema.org and Bioschemas.org:** [Schema.org](https://schema.org/) is a community effort to add semantic markup to web pages, supported by the main search engines and widely used. Bioschemas is a collection of opinionated profiles and types of Schema.org markup for the Life Sciences, developed by an open community sponsored by ELIXIR. Used for web based resources to be harvested and indexed by search engines and other services and registries, and by other services as a convenient common schema mechanism for consistent use of structured information. This is a key FAIR metadata component of the ELIXIR Tools ecosystem and EOSC-Life Workflow collaboratory as well as used by other registries and repositories in ELIXIR, and work is on-going in EOSC-Enhance to harvest Bioschemas into the OpenAIRE Research Graph.

IBISBAHub will use Bioschemas markup, not just for workflows but all its content types, and much of IBISBAHub is already marked up with schema.org terms. IBISBA are already leading

⁷⁸ Ojsteršek. (2021). Crosswalk of most used metadata schemes and guidelines for metadata interoperability (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4420116>

areas of Bioschema and lead the development of the Computational Workflow profile, used by WorkflowHub. The IBISBA Web site and One Stop Shop must also be consistently marked up.

- **DCAT:** A recommendation of The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), an [international community](#) that develops open [standards](#) to ensure the long-term growth of the Web. DCAT enables a publisher to describe datasets and data services in a catalog using a standard model and vocabulary that facilitates the consumption and aggregation of metadata from multiple catalogs. Aggregated DCAT metadata can serve as a manifest file as part of the digital preservation process. DCAT is widely used by other ESRIs and maps to Schema.org). *IBISBHub will need to implement or crosswalk to DCAT for its content.*
- **DataCite**⁷⁹ is an organisation that issues DOIs for research outputs such as publications and other digital objects datasets alongside metadata⁸⁰. *IBISBAHub supports publication and the assignment of DOIs for all its content, and will need to comply with the DataCite metadata schema.*
- **DDI-CDI**⁸¹ The Data Documentation Initiative Alliance/CODATA specification aimed at helping implementers integrate data across domain and institutional boundaries. A universal common model to describe data and its provenance at a detailed, machine-actionable level in order to bridge and integrate datasets described in different formats (e.g. DCAT or schema.org) along with processes and provenance. *The cost of adoption is high against unclear benefits when compared to lighter weight approaches like DCAT and schema.org, and simple cross-walks. FAIRsFAIR and CODATA are strong advocates of DDI-CDI.*

IBISBA will participate in the schema.org and bioschemas communities to ensure that any missing concepts are developed and added to the markup's capability. PREP-IBISBA must follow and where useful participate in other markup regimens. For example: DataCite, DCAT, Dublin Core⁸², Egeria Open Metadata and Governance⁸³, and Open Archives Initiative⁸⁴. Where suitable the markup used by IBISBA should be extended to use these standards.

Domain and type specific standards for Modular Service interoperability

Data generated by facilities, possibly passed to other facilities, and registered on IBISBAHub should be in a form that is FAIR and understandable by the facilities and IBISBAHub. For modular service handoffs as part of a meta-protocol data and quality control and harmonisation is essential. As well as standardised reporting of protocols and mandatory registration of protocols for review by authorised parties, each step needs standardised input data formats and output data formats.

There are two mechanisms that may be used:

- ***the format and content of the data can be explicitly specified in metadata about the data*** e.g. using *annotations* from the EDAM ontology. EDAM is a comprehensive ontology of well-

⁷⁹ <https://datacite.org/>

⁸⁰ https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.3/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.3.pdf

⁸¹ <https://ddi-alliance.atlassian.net/wiki/x/IQBPMw>.

⁸² <https://www.dublincore.org/>

⁸³ <https://egeria.odpi.org/>

⁸⁴ <https://openarchives.org/>

established, familiar concepts that are prevalent within computational biology, bioinformatics, and bioimage informatics. EDAM includes types of data and data identifiers, data formats, operations, and topics related to data analysis in life sciences and provides a set of concepts with preferred terms and synonyms, related terms, definitions, and other information. EDAM is particularly suitable for semantic annotations and categorisation of diverse resources related to bioscientific data analysis: e.g. tools, workflows, or training materials. EDAM is also useful in data management, for recording provenance metadata of processed bioscientific data.

- **IBISBA enforces restrictions on what formats and content can be exchanged between facilities.** PREP-IBISBA must recommend and enforce the set of formats to be used for data. The formats currently recommended for IBISBA1.0 are reported in IBISBA1.0 Deliverable D7.2 (table 2).

Data typology	Format	Data typology	Format
Bioparts	FASTA , Genbank	Optimization & design	SBML V3
Biological models	SBML V3	Molecule	InChI string , PDB
Experimental data	mzML , CSV , FASTQ , Excel	Workflows	CWL Common Workflow Language
Documents	PDF , Word , Plain Text		

Table 2 Data formats

Data template support

IBISBAHub has been extended to support the definition of *file templates* that may be followed by data registered in IBISBAHub. It also supports the specification of the type and format of the data that claims to conform to the template. The type and format are currently defined by EDAM entries.

Rightfield⁸⁵ is an open-source tool provided by the FAIRDOM-SEEK Consortium for adding ontology term selection to Excel spreadsheets: a 'Template Creator' creates semantically aware Excel spreadsheet templates that are then reused to collect and annotate data. Rightfield enabled templates can be prepared as part of the project Data Management Plan and force adherence to formats for handoffs between facilities as well as reporting and possible deposition in public archives.

IBISBA will need to extend and enforce the use of file templates and use of Rightfield and similar helper tools. This would be extremely useful for generic formats such as CSV, Excel, and Word.

⁸⁵ <https://rightfield.org.uk/>

FAIR Digital Objects

A FAIR Digital Object (FDO)⁸⁶ is defined as “a unit composed of data and/or metadata regulated by structures or schemas, and with an assigned globally unique and persistent identifier (PID), which is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable both by humans and computers for the reliable interpretation and processing of the data represented by the object”. FAIR Digital Objects were highlighted in the EC’s [Turning FAIR Into Reality](#)⁸⁷ 2018 report. The FAIR Digital Objects Forum has been established, spinning out from the RDA Data Fabric Interest Group. IBISBA members have attended and presented at meetings of both.

RO-Crate⁸⁸ has been proposed for the implementation of FAIR Digital Objects⁸⁹ on the World Wide Web as a common representation of the FDO Metadata objects foreseen by the FDO Framework and EOSC Interoperability Framework. Combined with FAIR Signposting⁹⁰ for resolving persistent identifiers to the FDO components these RO-Crates are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable by machines to both create and obtain the information they need to function.

[RO-Crate](#) is a community-lead standard to practically achieve FAIR packaging of Research Objects with their structured metadata. RO-Crate is used for reporting, service exchange, registry and repository deposition, import and export, archiving and citation. It is based on well-established Web standards, using JSON-LD with [schema.org](#) for its common metadata representation, but extensible with domain-specific vocabularies in a growing range of specialized RO-Crate profiles. These include, for example earth sciences [[Corcho et al 2021](#)], and the biodiversity in the DISSCO Specimen Data Refinery. Support for RO-Crate is being included in general data repositories DataVerse and Zenodo, is actively developed by the CS₃MESH₄EOSC community, and support is being developed for RO-Crate harvesting by the OpenAIRE EOSC infrastructure.

RO-Crate is used extensively in the EOSC-Life Workflow Collaboratory [[Goble et al 2021](#)] to exchange workflows between services, including the WorkflowHub, LifeMonitor⁹¹, which supports workflow testing, and workflow management systems such as Galaxy. An RO-Crate profile (recommending specific content for conformant RO-Crates) has been created for ComputationalWorkflows⁹². The IBISBA1.0 team were lead developers of this profile.

RO-Crates support any kind of digital object and commonly reference objects - thus making them metadata objects linking together objects hosted on different platforms. The FAIRDOME-SEEK implements RO-Crate features so IBISBAHub can easily adopt this increasingly popular metadata exchange mechanism.

IBISBA proposes to use RO-Crates as key mechanism for the IBISBA Interoperability Framework, for:

⁸⁶ De Smedt, K., Koureas, D., Wittenburg, P. (2020). FAIR Digital Objects for Science: From Data Pieces to Actionable Knowledge Units. Publications 8 (2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/publications8020021>

⁸⁷ <http://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

⁸⁸ <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

⁸⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5060284>

⁹⁰ <https://signposting.org/FAIR/>

⁹¹ https://crs4.github.io/life_monitor/

⁹² <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/profiles.html#workflow-ro-crate-profile>

- transferring information between facilities that are part of a multi-facility project
- encapsulating the project specification, reports, and results;
- shadowing digital objects held in external repositories or registries in the IBISBAHub; for example: workflows between IBISBAHub and WorkflowHub;
- participation in the EOSC-Life Workflow Collaboratory - submission of a workflow with input data to a workflow executor and acceptance of the results of workflow execution etc;
- exchanging with RO-Crate-enabled EOSC registries such as OpenAIRE;
- depositing into long-term EOSC archives such as Zenodo.

PREP-IBISBA Task 8.4 will identify the different types of RO-Crate that should be used by IBISBA, collaborate with the RO-Crate community to create any new RO-Crate profiles and seek wider (non-IBISBA) input to profile specifications and support for RO-Crate use.

APIs

Application Programmatic Interfaces are the programmatic glue between services, enabling systems to interact / interface with each other. All the components of IBISBA Core will implement APIs following a standard, such as JSONAPI⁹³ and fully documented, for example in the OpenAPI Specification⁹⁴. Community API standards, such as GA4GH, should be adopted, for example the GA4GH Tools Registry Service⁹⁵. Where facilities manage data stores with APIs these may be used to handle automated interaction with the IBISBAHub; otherwise CS3 services will be used.

Persistent Identifiers

Support for Persistent IDentifiers (PIDs) is included in the EOSC Core Minimum Viable Product and is at the heart of any interoperability framework. PIDs are also a core prerequisite to FAIR Compliance.

IBISBA should adopt a subset of the schemes registered within identifiers.org. Previous work in IBISBA 1.0 produced a list of recommendations (IBISBA Del 7.2, table 3), and the Life Science community has published recommendations for PID best practice⁹⁶.

Compartment: MetNetX compartment	Chemical: SABIO-RK chemical MetaNetX chemical	Compound: KEGG compound PubChem-compound
Substance: PubChem-substance	Models: BioModels	General: DOI, PubMed, ORCID, ATCC

Table 3: The identification schemes currently recommended from IBISBA 1.0

⁹³ <https://jsonapi.org/>

⁹⁴ <https://swagger.io/specification/>

⁹⁵ <https://ga4gh.github.io/tool-registry-service-schemas/>

⁹⁶ McMurry JA, Juty N, Blomberg N, Burdett T, Conlin T, Conte N, et al. (2017) Identifiers for the 21st century: How to design, provision, and reuse persistent identifiers to maximize utility and impact of life science data. PLoS Biol 15(6): e2001414. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.2001414>

Where data is registered into IBISBAHub but *retained and stored by the facility*, in order for that data to be FAIR it must be permanently accessible. This requires that each facility adhere to the IBISBA policy for the creation of standard Global Persistent Identifiers.

Governance policies in IBISBA must monitor the persistence of recommended identifiers in registries, repositories and stores and propose remedial action if necessary.

3.4 Metadata and FAIR Data Services

FAIR Data Services provide key services for managing metadata, ontologies, and identifiers; testing for FAIR compliance, registries for sources of information etc. Examples identified in Deliverable 8.1 and more include the following:

- **FAIRsharing** - registry of curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies.
- **FAIRassist**⁹⁷ - tool for assessing FAIR compliance.
- **Identifiers.org** - registry for resolvable (dereferenceable) URIs for existing database identifiers, which are intended to be stable over time and independent of the provider.
- **NCBI Taxonomy Browser**⁹⁸ - registry for finding organisms.
- **Ontology Lookup Service**⁹⁹ - registry for ontologies for vocabularies.
- **Ontology mapping service**¹⁰⁰ - for mapping between vocabulary terms.
- **BridgeDB**¹⁰¹ - registry for mapping between identifiers.

For FAIR Data registries where entry values are used by IBISBA Core services, notably IBISBAHub, strategies are needed to synchronise and keep up with updates to the registries. For identifiers, Identifiers.org guarantees that if a resource that will resolve the identifier exists, the identifiers.org URI will always work by pointing at it. However, resources merge and change identifiers and this must be catered for.

3.5 Intellectual property (IPR), accessibility, availability and licensing

Data is *available* if it is there and then *accessible* by appropriate protocols under appropriate conditions. Intellectual property (IPR) is one of the major concerns within IBISBA. It can be owned by different members of a project (e.g. the executing facilities, project owner or the IBISBA consortium). Knowledge that is obtained during projects are difficult to allocate to the respective groups. Agreements can be made on the ownership and accessibility of digital objects.

Through the registration of digital objects in the IBISBAHub, members can be associated with or *restricted from access* thereby ensuring that objects are not shared accidentally with the wrong partner. The accessibility is managed by restricting the permission of an object, only to a person, a group, a project or when published as completely open.

⁹⁷ <https://fairassist.org/#/>

⁹⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Taxonomy/Browser>

⁹⁹ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/index>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/spot/oxo/>

¹⁰¹ <https://bridgedb.github.io/>

Digital objects are further secured through a *license* which could indicate that an object can be freely shared without restrictions or is not allowed to be exchanged via any means to another / external partner. Licenses can vary from extremely strict e.g. or completely open e.g. cco. Through licensing it is possible to control the level of shareability by law allowing it to be shared for example with academic institutes but not commercial enterprises.

It is essential that assets of IBISBA must have a license, or explicitly declare that there is no license i.e. no reuse/sharing is allowed. A default license needs to be defined and agreed with Infrastructure partners. There are a number of standard repositories for licenses such as spdx.org. PREP-IBISBA will follow spdx.org. Where additional information is needed to fill in the license information then IBISBAHub will be extended to hold that information. It is possible that facilities will have licenses tied to them e.g. Facility A is always MIT which will need to be respected.

Further security requirements can be put in place by using *locally managed data storage* under the control of respective facilities or national nodes and only register the metadata concerning such data objects. With the retention of data control some responsibilities to be carried by the facilities or national nodes:

- data storage needs to be accessible through network interfaces using standard / open communication protocols. Access cannot be to local devices like a usb-drive or a personal computer. By registering the metadata of a data object in IBISBAHub the data's location is verified to be to some extent accessible through a network protocol. When this is not adhered to (e.g. when using a local file path) the data object cannot be registered into the Hub.
- data must be identifiable and accessible with a Persistent ID.
- access may need authorization and authentication of facility or node-specific user credentials; these must not be kept within IBISBA and they must be requested from the user when the link to the asset is followed.
- facility or node must have a retention policy that conforms with that of IBISBA.
- sharing specified on IBISBAHub for the registration link must match the actual sharing of the asset at the facility and be validated that this is the case.

3.6 Digital Security

Security is of prime concern to IBISBA users. Security applies to all the components of the digital infrastructure - the centralised IBISBAHub and storage and the data repositories held by facilities/nodes or by sister infrastructures. There are many strands to security:

- communication - can information being passed be intercepted
- site identification - can sites be readily identified as the expected site (both to a user and to another computer)
- authentication - is the person (or computer) attempting to access information, actually who they claim to be
- authorization - is an authenticated person allowed to access the information, and, if so, to what extent

- intra-site authentication and authorization - a site e.g. a facility must still be able to enforce its own security mechanisms
- understandable licenses - the users of a system must be able to recognize and easily interpret the license under which information is made available. Common license registries exist, and these must be used
- facility oriented - any IBISBA infrastructure and security must always take account of the fact that data is produced at facilities and passed between them.

The most tested part (for security) of the IBISBA infrastructure is IBISBAHub. It is recommended that other parts of the IBISBA Core should use IBISBAHub's security mechanisms to ensure they have the correct access to assets. Table 4 summarises security issues to address.

Secure communication	<p>This applies to communication between the: customer and IBISBACentral; customer and the facilities; facilities; facilities and IBISBA infrastructure e.g. IBISBAHub; and different parts of the IBISBA infrastructure.</p> <p><i>All communication should use secure protocols e.g. HTTPS and not HTTP. For e-mails this will be difficult to institute, but IBISBA should investigate the use of a system such as Proton mail from CERN. IBISBA should also investigate the possibility of using a VPN, at least between different parts of its infrastructure providing an extra layer of security.</i></p>
Site phishing appearance	<p>It is normal for a set of sites to use the same domain. Users often interpret a change in domain as an attempt at phishing i.e. tricking them into going to a different "rogue" site.</p> <p><i>All sites that are part of the IBISBA infrastructure must be part of the ibisba.eu domain.</i></p>
Ownership of ibisba.eu	<p>Domains are registered for a limited time period, and then need renewal. Registration by a specific person now unavailable, or who has forgotten the details, causes difficulties.</p> <p><i>The ibisba.eu domain must be registered by an address that resolves to a set of people designated by the IBISBA consortium.</i></p>
Security certificates ownership	<p>The identification of a site is separate from the registration of a site, using security certificates.</p> <p><i>The security certificates for the IBISBA sites must be under the control of the IBISBA consortium. Although domain registrars commonly will also issue security certificates for the registered site, it is preferable that the certificates are obtained from a separate supplier. This makes the hosting of the domain elsewhere easier.</i></p>
Expiration of security certificates	<p>Security certificates are only valid for a limited time period. Expiration commonly results in the site being interpreted as insecure or as bogus. Expiration of the security certificates must be monitored and auto-renewed.</p> <p><i>An identified set of people within the IBISBA consortium must be responsible for dealing with messages from the security monitor, and for the renewal of the certificates.</i></p>
Off-site linkage	<p>If a link with a web page links to another site, especially one that is not part of the same domain, then it is confusing for users, and often interpreted as a security risk.</p> <p><i>Where an IBISBA site links off to a site in another domain, this must be explicit and obvious. For example, the external site could be opened in a new tab / window. It must never appear as if an external site is part of the IBISBA domain</i></p>

Site branding	To encourage brand recognition, and to reassure users as to IBISBA's validity. <i>All IBISBA Core Services must have consistent branding. A good start has been made in this area e.g. by the development of a common logo.</i>
API "logout"	APIs that keep the communicating computer "logged in" causing problems when each individual communication is authorized and authenticated. <i>Careful thought and analysis must be done of all APIs used within IBISBA to identify any access "remains" and either remove, mitigate or carefully document the API's "feature".</i>
Information visibility	Access to a file of data should be controlled, but could also apply to knowledge of the mere existence of a project of work being carried out by the IBISBA consortium. <i>Analysis is required for what needs to be allowed to be kept private.</i>
Visibility confusion	Different parts of the IBISBA Core may have differing ideas as to what should be visible. The website could promote a "success story" for a project totally private in IBISBAHub. <i>All parts of the IBISBA infrastructure should have consistent content and access views</i> There may be wider initiatives to specify authorization, authentication and access capabilities. For example, ELIXIR AAI has some capability in this area. IBISBA must adopt the solution that best allows it to operate in an open heterogeneous environment.

Table 4 Summarises security issues to address.

3.7 RDM Lifecycle using the proposed digital framework

IBISBA's goal is to support FAIR by Design: from the first steps of producing FAIR data and Data Management Planning to the final steps of depositing data in public archives and enabling its reuse. Thus data will need to be managed at every step of the Research Data lifecycle as defined by ELIXIR's RDM toolkit RDMkit¹⁰². The RDMkit and its associated tools (Data Stewardship Wizard) and registries (TeSS, FAIRsharing, bio.tools, WorkflowHub) will be incorporated into IBISBA's digital framework as seen in section 3.2. Table 5 summarises the services.

	Plan	Collect	Process	Analyse	Preserve	Share	Reuse
One Stop Shop							
iPOP							
TasCu							
Rightfield							
Protocols.io							
IBISBAHub							
Galaxy - SynBioCad							
COPASI							
JWS Online							

¹⁰² <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org>

WorkflowHub							
Bio.tools							
ELIXIR AAI							
Handbook							
BPM							
RDMkit & DSW							
FAIRsharing							
identifier.org							
Storage and Compute services							

Table 5 Services against the RDM life cycle. **Green bold** are services internal to IBISBA, developed in IBISBA1.0 and PREP-IBISBA as part of the sandbox (Task 8.4)

4 Conclusion

This deliverable set out the preliminary architecture for the FAIR IBISBA digital infrastructure. It makes extensive use of pilot developments in IBISBA 1.0 and resources in EOSC and sister ESFRIs to IBISBA, and aligns with current EOSC strategies. This will assist its sustainability planning.

The adoption and operational deployment of the infrastructure depends on development and adoption of processes, buy-in from the IBISBA partners and facilities through Service Level Agreements and commitments to policies and the RDM skills of the facility operators and data stewards (figure 10).

Figure 10 Technical infrastructure is only part of successful adoption of a digital infrastructure

Next steps are to:

- Assemble a **“sandbox” implementation** for supporting the preparatory stage of EU-IBISBA using candidate components to demonstrate and assess readiness (Task 8.4);

- Work with WP6 for developing the **Project Management** subsystem;
- Develop **policies and a roadmap for capacity building** for FAIR asset stewardship among EU-IBISBA members (Task 8.5);
- Develop **policies and Service Level Agreements** for Facility and Nodes for RDM and obligations to the IBISBA digital platform;
- Develop **delivery partnerships and procurement policies** for storage and data services where necessary;
- Develop **governance policies** for preservation, licencing and access.

5 Partners involved in the work

UNIMAN: Carole Goble, Alan Williams, Munazah Andrabi

WUR: Jasper Koehorst

VTT: Gopal Peddinti, Matti Kannisto, Peter Blomberg

UAB: Joan Albiol Sala

6. Abbreviations

EOSC - European Open Science Cloud

SOP – Standard Operating Procedure

TNA – Trans National Access

ELIXIR – European Research Infrastructure for Life Science Data

RDM – Research Data Management

FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

SOP – Standard Operating Procedure

DBTL-S – Design, Built, Test, Learn-Scale

TRL – Technology Readiness Level